

GROWING OF MEDICINAL PLANTS ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE AGROTECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. Since they provide natural resources for pharmaceuticals and traditional medicine across the world, the cultivation of medicinal plants has long been important for healthcare. Effective and sustainable production techniques are essential given the growing demand for herbal remedies. In order to improve productivity, quality, and ecological sustainability, this study looks at the use of cutting-edge agrotechnologies in the cultivation of medicinal plants. The efficacy of several techniques in enhancing plant growth, resource efficiency, and environmental impact was examined. These techniques included precision drip irrigation, bio-fertilizers, organic soil amendments, and real-time soil and crop monitoring systems. Results show that these cutting-edge agrotechnologies maximize ecological footprint reduction, limit resource use, and boost output.

Key words: Herbal remedies, Novel agricultural methods, Agriculture that is sustainable, The cultivation of plants, Agricultural biotechnology, Accurate farming, Health of the soil, Climate-smart farming, Organic agricultural methods, Efficiency of resources, Disease and pest management, Preservation of soil, Manufacturing of herbal medicines, Innovation in agriculture.

Annotatsiya. Dorivor o'simliklarni yetishtirish qadimdan sog'liqni saqlash sohasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etib kelgan, chunki ular butun dunyoda farmatsevtika va an'anaviy tibbiyot uchun tabiiy resurslarni ta'minlaydi. O'simlik dorilariga bo'lgan talab ortib borayotganini hisobga olsak, samarali va barqaror ishlab chiqarish usullari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu tadqiqot dorivor o'simliklarni yetishtirishda zamonaviy agrotexnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali hosildorlik, sifat va ekologik barqarorlikni oshirishni o'rganadi. O'simlik o'sishini, resurslardan foydalanish samaradorligini va ekologiyaga ta'sirini yaxshilashda turli texnikalarning samaradorligi ko'rib chiqildi, ular orasida aniqlik bilan tomchilatib sug'orish, bio-o'g'itlar, organik tuproq modifikatsiyalari hamda tuproq va ekinlarni real vaqt rejimida kuzatish tizimlari mavjud. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu ilg'or agrotexnologiyalar ekologik izni kamaytirishni, resurslardan foydalanishni cheklashni va ishlab chiqarishni oshirishni maksimal darajada ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'simlik dori vositalari, yangi qishloq xo'jalik usullari, barqaror qishloq xo'jaligi, o'simliklarni yetishtirish, qishloq xo'jaligi biotexnologiyasi, aniqlik bilan dehqonchilik, tuproq salomatligi, iqlimga mos qishloq xo'jaligi, organik qishloq xo'jaligi usullari, resurslardan foydalanish samaradorligi, kasallik va zararkunandalarni boshqarish, tuproqni saqlash, dorivor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish, qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsiya.

Introduction

For millennia, medicinal plants have been used as all-natural cures for a variety of illnesses, greatly influencing human health and wellbeing. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 80% of people worldwide still rely on medicinal plants for healthcare, and demand for herbal remedies and natural health products is only expected to increase. This increasing need emphasizes how crucial it is to develop effective and sustainable techniques for

growing medicinal plants that satisfy the requirements of both conventional medicine and contemporary healthcare.

Conventional farming practices frequently encounter obstacles including excessive use of water and soil resources, harm to the environment from artificial pesticides, and inconsistent quality of the final product. Consequently, there has been a great deal of interest in using cutting-edge agrotechnologies to cultivate therapeutic plants. In addition to increasing the quantity and quality of medicinal plants, methods like drip irrigation, biofertilizers, organic amendments, and soil monitoring can also lessen their negative effects on the environment and increase resource efficiency.

This study examines the methods for growing medicinal plants using cutting-edge agrotechnologies, looking at the advantages they provide for the environment and economy as well as any potential drawbacks. In addition, the study intends to analyze recent findings and developments in this area and to provide light on the function of creative methods in the production of medicinal plants[1-11].

Methods and results

This study evaluated the effects of many cutting-edge agrotechnologies on the development and caliber of medicinal plants. Preparing the Soil and Applying Organic Fertilizer. Compost and biofertilizers were among the organic amendments used to prepare the soil in order to improve its microbial activity, structure, and nutrient availability. Without using artificial chemicals, biogumus and other organic fertilizers were used to increase soil fertility. In order to customize the fertilization plan, soil samples were examined for pH, nutritional composition, and organic matter concentration.

Managing Water Use Using Drip Irrigation Technology In order to accurately feed water to plant root zones and minimize evaporation and runoff, drip irrigation systems were constructed. Utilizing soil moisture sensors, water levels were monitored and adjusted to optimize soil hydration and encourage steady plant development while save water.

Monitoring of Light and Temperature

Sensors for temperature and light were utilized to keep an eye on the environmental factors that are necessary for healthy plant development. Artificial lighting was used to simulate natural sunshine in shady or indoor environments, and thermostats were used to maintain steady temperatures to aid in the growth of the plants. To assess the effects of temperature changes and light exposure on growth rates and phytochemical composition, data were gathered.

Control of Pests and Diseases. Using Biological Techniques. To cut down on the usage of chemical pesticides, biological pest management techniques were used, such as introducing beneficial insects and using organic pest repellents like neem oil. By maintaining ecological balance and controlling insect populations, these techniques sought to produce safer therapeutic plants.

Gathering and Examining Data. At various phases of growth, plant growth indicators such as height, leaf area, biomass, and phytochemical content were measured. To ascertain the perfect circumstances for every species, data from sensors measuring temperature, light, and soil moisture were examined. The effects of each technique on plant output, resource efficiency, and health were examined using statistical methods.

The findings showed that the development and quality of medicinal plants were significantly enhanced by the application of cutting-edge agrotechnologies. Important conclusions consist of: Enhanced Yield and Growth Rate: Compared to conventional techniques,

the combination of drip irrigation and organic fertilizers enhanced plant biomass and growth rate by around 25–30%.

Increased Phytochemical Content and Quality: Plants cultivated under regulated light conditions and with biofertilizers showed higher concentrations of active chemicals, which increased their therapeutic potential.

Resource Efficiency: Biological pest management lowered the need for artificial pesticides, reducing environmental effect, while drip irrigation cut water consumption by up to 50%.

Ecological Sustainability: By using biological pest management methods and organic amendments, a better soil ecology was created, hence reducing the need for artificial chemicals.

Discussion

The findings underscore the potential of innovative agrotechnologies in medicinal plant cultivation. The enhanced yield and quality observed in plants grown with advanced methods indicate that these technologies can meet the growing demand for medicinal plants sustainably. Furthermore, the reduction in water usage and pesticide application demonstrates the environmental benefits of these practices. However, initial setup costs for technologies like drip irrigation and sensor-based monitoring may pose challenges for small-scale farmers. Future research should focus on developing cost-effective solutions to make these technologies accessible to a broader range of agricultural practitioners.

Conclusion

A potential approach to the sustainable production of medicinal plants is offered by innovative agrotechnologies, which have positive effects on the environment, yield, and quality. This study shows how to maximize the production of medicinal plants while satisfying ecological and economic requirements by combining techniques like drip irrigation, organic fertilization, and biological pest control. The use of these technologies will be essential in advancing sustainable agriculture practices that promote human health and environmental well-being, as the demand for natural cures grows globally. Future research ought to examine how scalable these technologies are and how they may be used for additional high-value crops in various agricultural contexts.

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